

Paigatasa and South Gimi are off-road, subsistence farming communities in Okapa District, Eastern Highlands Province, Papua New Guinea, with an estimated population of up to 10,000 people. Health statistics for Okapa demonstrate poor access to perinatal careⁱ, with the common practice of home births unattended by trained health workers, and very limited access to health care in pre-pregnancy, pregnancy and the postpartum and neonatal stagesⁱⁱ, both of which are linked to a higher rate of maternal and neonatal deaths and other undesirable perinatal health outcomes. In 2010, women from Paigatasa Clinic catchment area primarily cited distance and cost reasons for deciding to birth at home in the three years leading up to the study, and specified the following issues:

- unavailability of accommodation in Goroka,
- children, gardens and other responsibilities at home,
- lack of funds and transport to travel to a health centre,
- dangers of travel,
- no escort for journey,
- preference to give birth at home in a traditional way,
- dissatisfaction with health care, and
- parents-in-law insisting on a home birth.

Table 21: Reasons for birthing at home	Paiga	Outlying areas	Total*	Percent
Own wish	2 (14%)	0	2	3%
Parents or husband insist	0	0	0	-
In-laws insist	0	3 (9%)	3	6%
No transport	0	2 (6%)	2	4%
No road	0	0	0	-
No money	5 (35%)	13 (39%)	18	38%
Health facility too far	6 (42%)	14 (42%)	20	43%
Only male health workers	0	0	0	-
Other (not safe to travel, nowhere to stay, etc)	3 (21%)	6 (18%)	9	19%
Total home/<i>smallhaus</i> deliveries, last 3 years	14/28 (50%)	33/45 (73%)	47/73**	64%

*More than one response possible. **One stillbirth included in these figuresⁱⁱⁱ.

The catchment community, through the Paigatasa Clinic Committee, have requested that PAIGA (Peoples of Australasia for Innovation and Growth Abroad) organisation^{iv} fund and coordinate the construction of a Maternity Waiting Home (MWH) in Goroka, to reduce financial and distance barriers to supervised hospital births and emergency maternal and neonatal care (EMONC).

Additional benefits to families using Goroka Hospital include:

- access to antenatal STI testing,
- appropriate care for high risk pregnancies,
- the opportunity to rest before giving birth,
- birth registration,
- post-birth contraceptive options,
- health education, and
- maternal and infant immunisations.

A literature review on MWHs globally has demonstrated that in settings with good standards of secondary/tertiary maternal and neonatal care, MWHs will support better maternal and neonatal outcomes^v. While MWH initiatives are largely unreported in PNG, one project in Alotau Province has been successful in increasing supervised hospital births and reducing maternal and infant deaths by offering community-based education for health workers and families, transport, accommodation, and mother & baby gifts for those delivering in hospital^{vi}.

Recommendations for making MWHs acceptable in other settings include:

- supporting traditional practices,
- respect from staff,
- direct costs of hospital and medicines covered,
- transport and lost labour compensated for,
- more contraceptive options to improve uptake of modern methods and avoid side effects and reversion to unreliable traditional methods,
- consideration of alternative 'safe' delivery methods when villages are inaccessible because of weather or with unexpected or premature births,
- alternative childcare arrangements to avoid older children missing school, and
- training in handicrafts to enable women's income generating activities^{vii}.

Scoping study

PAIGA Committee sought to gather evidence from community members of acceptability and intention to use a MWH, should one be established in Goroka for the Paigatasa Clinic catchment community. The scoping research question and study objectives were:

What are women's and their families' thoughts on use of a waiting home, for and against, and what could make this project a success or failure?

A qualitative scoping study was undertaken with eight community members, including five women of childbearing age, and three men who represented marital partners, fathers, local community health workers (CHWs) and clinic committee members. Women's ages ranged from 23 to 48 (estimated age), and men's ages from late 40s to late 50s. All participants except one of the two interpreters were from Paigatasa community, and all were parents of at least one child. The three older women had husbands, and the younger two were single. Two of the older women and one man were illiterate or semi-literate. A male or female interpreter (English-Tok Pisin or English-South Fore) was used to match participant gender, and semi-structured interview format was trialled with interpreters prior to using with participants. Interpreter responses to interview questions have also been used in the survey where relevant. All participants were read a consent statement and verbally consented to participating in the study. Participants were compensated for time and travel expenses to the Goroka AT Projects Guesthouse where the study took place, and accommodation and meals were provided, along with small gifts for each participant. Interpreters were compensated for time with small gifts and an agreed sum in local currency, and accommodation and meals were provided where required.

Survey questions were designed to gather qualitative information about women's and their partners' knowledge of reproductive health and services prior to pregnancy, past birth experiences and decision-making around uptake of services, and participants' attitudes towards the proposed MWH.

A focus group involving all participants was held after the individual interviews, to discuss practical aspects of establishing a MWH including land ownership, design and facilities to be offered.

Findings from the survey have been presented using mixed implementation and phenomenological research approaches^{viii} for local context analysis, under broad question headings. Findings are reported from the perspectives of women participants and of husband, parent and health worker participants.

1. Personal decision-making re: birthing choices

Women were invited to tell the stories of their experiences of giving birth. The number of deliveries per woman ranged from two to five; participants described a total of 18 births. Two of the five women had their first child at home. All women had healthy babies; one woman's child died at 12 years of age. Most women had uncomplicated labours, although one described a 48-hour labour that caused transient swelling of her baby's head, another a transverse lie that self-corrected prior to labour, and two women described face, arm and leg swelling in late pregnancy. Two potentially life-threatening labour complications treated in hospital were reported (hypertensive disorder of pregnancy with induced premature birth, and retained products requiring surgical removal).

Experiences ranged from all hospital births (interpreter), to all home births (young unmarried woman). One birth took place unintentionally on the way to a rural health centre: "I was trying myself to go to the clinic, but it was in the night... I had to walk... I felt that the baby was close to delivery, and it's quite a long way, so I decided to stay with someone." More recent births were either at Goroka Hospital or at home, whereas some births and postpartum care in the 1990s and 2000s took place at Henagaru, Ivingoi and Okapa health centres, reflecting the recent decline in rural maternity services.

Literacy did not seem to affect women's choice of home birth in the sample group. However, having a partner did make it easier for women to access health facility births: "If I was married, it would be easy, but it's not easy if I'm not married." Unmarried women also reported a problem regarding the care of their other children if they were to travel to give birth in hospital. "My first born, my father treats him like his last-born son, and stays with my parents, but [second son] stays with me. If I was married, my husband would look after [second son] while I had another baby." One unmarried woman reported that she delivered her second baby at home as her parents were angry that she had fallen pregnant a second time before finishing her schooling, and they had refused to fund her travel to Goroka.

All community women reported that health facility births were dependent on having relatives to stay with.

Having funds to travel and stay in Goroka was important: "I would pick coffee, save money to come here [Goroka]. If not, no choice, I would have to stay in the village." One woman estimated the total cost of giving birth at Goroka Hospital then having her tubes tied for family completion to be 300-500 kina, including transport, healthcare-associated fees and the cost of staying with relatives. There was a cost described for all formal peripartum care: antenatal care, labour, immunisations (50t), family planning (K4), and baby health books (K5); this cost was reported to be increasing over time.

Distance to Goroka Hospital was a concern with the chance of the baby arriving early: "From the village to the bus stop it's a bit long way, and when we are walking, we are getting scared that... the kid will get born along the way, so we have to walk fast to make it to the bus stop, get the PMV and make it to town."

Health worker advice, family attitudes and availability of family to assist also played a part in women's decisions to birth in hospital or at home. Most women reported being advised by health workers to give birth in hospital, and the older women also felt that "sometimes in the village, they can't, you know, clean you well, and you can face problems," and "...some ladies, they die because of problems giving birth in the village," and "I'm not feeling good for my family or relatives, to... see me giving birth. Hospital is the right place to give birth. The doctors and nurses, that's their job." One woman said that she chose to have her third baby in Goroka Hospital because "[t]here was no one to help in the village. My mother-in-law was in Port Moresby..."

Participants are all from Paigatasa community that has a longstanding CHW, so had access to antenatal care near their homes. All women participants sought antenatal care, and postnatal care for their babies. Postnatal care involved vaccinations for the baby, but not always a postnatal check for the mother. "4 months later we came to Goroka for immunisation, but no check for myself." Family planning was also offered for most postnatal visits, but not accepted by all women. Reasons for not accepting family planning amounted to fear of side effects, real or imagined, and availability. From one woman who had complications after labour leading to advice not to use depot contraception again: "They offer, but I say I've had [enough] of family planning, because I go through very big hard time, big tester, that's why I gave up on FP." From another: "I heard that ladies with family planning die." Sometimes, family planning was not available at the clinic the participant had attended due to stockouts.

One participant described her choice to stop at four babies, the practice of informal adoptions and the complexity of family connections: "I have FP – depo - and four is enough, no more. I have one girl, plus one adopted girl, and 3 boys, but one died at age 12. My husband's sister – the man's family wanted the child but not the sister. The husband's family wanted the kid but not her, so my family said we'll take the girl and adopt. The sister now has a second husband; she's the second wife. The first wife - no kids, so the second wife has kids and all are happy."

Husbands, fathers and a CHW also contributed their thoughts. When asked about a decision to space his and his wife's children five years apart, a male participant said: "Probably in traditional, [babies were born] one after another, then mother carry baby and young children and father axe to garden, gets crowded and bad. Burden. So space so they get strong enough and help with food and look after themselves, walk by themselves... Thinking of land I have and future of children, and how much coffee to feed, educate and clothe. I have much land. Three sons and one girl, so one more if boy or girl I have enough land, they will be ok."

A father spoke about how he and his family managed his unmarried daughter's pregnancies:

"[she] was studying Year 8 at Kabuye Primary when she got pregnant. We talked to the teachers and withdrew her from the school. Her boy was named after her uncle. When he was delivered, I asked my wife to breastfeed him. [She] finished Year 8, then went to Goroka School and finished Grade 9, then got pregnant a second time at school. I supported both kids for food and clothing, and [her] too. I wasn't angry at her. People were looking at me in the community, like bad. But I look after them like my own children. They don't know their dad so recognise me as their father when they grow up."

2. Knowledge and attitudes to sexual and reproductive health (self and family)

Women were asked about their knowledge of family planning, pregnancy and giving birth before their first pregnancies and after, and where that knowledge came from.

One unmarried young woman reported that she had learnt nothing about sexual and reproductive health before she fell pregnant: "... my parents didn't really talk to me about it," and "[w]hen I was that age, I was thinking how mothers give birth to a child, but no one informed me until by myself I experienced it."

Some women received sexual and reproductive health information from their mothers or big sisters before they became sexually active: "Yeah... she tells me, when you get married you will be like this, you will go through things like this, so she told me that when you marry and then you stay with your husband, and then you will get pregnant. And my big sister too, she normally encourages me. And I always ask questions, I normally ask my big sister. I ask her, 'How do women get their baby?' Because first I was thinking that they normally operate their stomach to get the baby... [gestures to navel]," and: "My big sister – she told me that a lady gets married, then she goes to her husband's place with special *bilums* and clothes. Then she became a mother - and she went through the experiences."

The *hausmeri* is a Fore tradition that takes place before a woman is married. The two older women who had married in the village talked about learning from senior women at this gathering.

One woman reported that her mother had told her: "...ladies with family planning don't have period and have back-ache. It made me scared." Later, after having another two children, she took advice from her CHW: "I accepted will get implant. Johnmark advised that." When asked what changed her mind: "I had no husband, and had a hard time with three kids without a husband." Another reported: "...we went to the baby clinic, and Dr Wery asked about family planning, so I had the depo shot."

Husbands played an important role in decision-making about family completion. Tubal ligation (TL) and vasectomy are the two permanent methods of contraception available in Goroka. One woman reported: "So I was thinking that I would go through TL to stop, you know, but they told me you would feel more pain enough, and you go tell your husband to stop, so you know, [husband's name] went through the [vasectomy]." A participant husband said: "I'm planning a vasectomy. They walk far for garden and carry firewood, so I don't want problems in the future if she has operation. It's easy for me to have the snip."

The importance of antenatal care in supporting decision-making was highlighted: "...the nurses normally tells us that when you are pregnant, and then they normally tells us that when you are 9 months, you feel pain, that means you are going to give birth, and you must come to the hospital. So, that's where I get some information from there, when I go for clinic." And: "When I went to the clinic, Denmark told me that this is my last month, and next month you will be dropping your baby, so you must go [to Goroka Hospital]."

One father reported relying on his daughter's word not to fall pregnant while at school: "I wanted to give [daughter] family planning after the first delivery, but [daughter] tricked and said I already have one [child], so I won't do it again. Then she did pregnancy again in Goroka,"

One father reported erroneous advice that the Health Department did not allow teenagers to learn about or use contraception: "...the Health Department say we can't give advice [on family planning] until 17 or 18 [years of age] – I did advise, but have to follow Health Department. She promised and I trusted." Other participants who were parents of teenagers did not mention contraceptive options as ways to keep their children safe from unwanted pregnancies, but instead talked about the problems of mobile phone technology introducing pornography to adolescents. They also raised the problem of how young women living with relatives in town to attend high school left them

vulnerable to unwanted pregnancy, suggesting that sex for favours from 'boyfriends' was a way of obtaining pocket money and meeting the cost of school supplies and other living needs while in town. One solution offered to this problem was to board their teenaged daughters at single-sex school dormitories, but this option was also considered too expensive for most families.

The CHW reported that: "I was given advice on how to provide info on family planning in age groups for 16, 17, 18 etc. We give specific advice. HIV from 13/14," and "...when they want treatment, I give. Info and advice in the marketplace, and in age groups in the church. When the community is in one place." The CHW also said that sexual and reproductive health education was not given to adolescents in schools, but that communities relied on CHWs to give education in the market and at church. "We have been teaching when young, in public place, at the clinic, the young ladies. I thought they were aware already and educated. They think it won't affect them. I provide services but their thinking is not there yet. Some listen and get family planning and they are ok. Others take risks and learn by reality."

One interviewer reported that: "...the girls in the school are getting pregnant in the school, and they remove them from the school and or something like that. Some are doing Grade 7 or 8." and "I was surprised and I said oh, this one get married too? And they said no, we don't know the father, but she's pregnant. And I said please, come on young girls...").

3. *Traditional attitudes to safe motherhood*

Women were asked about the community's traditional attitudes to FP, pregnancy and giving birth, and effects of these attitudes on their own SRH experiences.

One woman's mother gave the following advice when her menstrual period first started: "Don't go out with men, when it's your period don't cook or touch food or walk in front of boys/men." Another reported that she was given similar advice in pregnancy:

If you are expecting a baby or become pregnant, you will not see your period, and when you got through that stage, you must inform so that... When you are pregnant, that's the custom that no one will go at the back of me. That's the custom... I sit like this, so no-one can walk at the back of me. So if they want to go, I just bend down and they walk at the front. And when they cook the greens in the bamboo, like the one on the top and the bottom, I take the middle one and eat. I followed the custom. When you feel pain, they say you are feeling labour pains, so it's time for you to go.

Some traditional advice appeared to relate to a widespread local taboo intended to prevent men from being 'polluted' by women's blood, as has been reported in other studies on women's health in the Highlands^{ix}. Participants reported that this taboo did not extend to health workers or the hospital/health facility setting, or to pregnant women using public motor vehicles. However, the CHW reported that many other community women did not use his services for antenatal care or skilled birth attendance at home, as it was considered taboo to share that personal information with a man.

Some women participants talked about sex education in the *hausmeri*: "When my bride price was paid and I was getting dressed for being taken to meet my husband, I was in the *hausmeri* and was told then," and "...the old women tell stories and give actions [imitates having sex; laughs]. Tells the girls what to do. As a small child I saw these demonstrations," and "It's information on how to look after your husband, home, house, garden, kids to school," and "They talk about men do anything,

but all baby responsibility is yours, so don't get angry if they do their own thing. They don't talk family planning. They talk, 'Never hold onto your husband'. Some women get angry with their husbands and want them never to go away – I was taught never to be like that." One orphaned woman said: "*Hausmeri* was good for me, my parents died so I learnt a lot there. I don't know for others if their parents taught them more."

A husband talked about his traditional education in the *hausman*:

"...we had two to three weeks of stories on how to look after a wife, what to expect, signs of pregnancy, etcetera, how to be a husband, so when [my wife] said no period, I remembered the stories from *hausman* – old men's stories. [I was a] teenager – 17-18 years old – getting a beard, go to *hausman*... Old man tells boys that when women are going to have a baby, into *smallhaus*. She is there then home five days to a week, and the husband leaves the house for this period, then comes back. Not really any idea of family planning at the time of *hausman*."

Practices in the *smallhaus* or labouring hut were described in terms of untrained but experienced older female relatives assisting with labour: "Yagasi's wife and Afi, an old woman, the two women delivered the last baby in the *smallhaus*"; taboos around birth: "...in the village too it's very strict. When the ladies are giving birth, they normally stay in a *smallhaus*. So they can't cook, they just stay there, don't come out"; and common practices during delivery: "The story of my first birth, it was 1999 full moon in the eleventh month. In the morning, feeling pain, like toilet but no toilet. I talked to mother-in-law, 'The baby is coming!' Pain start and stop, get stronger and faster. I was gardening, picking greens, and felt pain when I stood up, so I went to the *smallhaus*. In the afternoon, 3 women helped, and the baby was born. It was a boy. They used a bamboo knife to cut the cord, tied and cauterised the belly button to stop the blood. I breastfed the baby, then the afterbirth was delivered and I was alright." Some assistance described involved active delivery of the placenta by an untrained person: "Mother-in-law said on-and-off pain equals a boy, constant pain means a girl. With the firstborn, the placenta followed quickly. With the second-born I pushed, struggled to get the placenta out. My mother-in-law wrapped the cord around her hand and pulled the placenta out. I stood up and felt no pain, so I was ok."

4. Church attitude to safe motherhood (opportunities and threats)

Women were asked about the teachings of their church about FP, pregnancy and giving birth. All reported that no teaching was given by their local church (Paigatasa Seventh Day Adventist or Baptist churches), but two women described attending Seventh Day Adventist church camps where health workers gave training on sexual and reproductive health: "In the village, no. In the big camp, yes, as they have doctors^x who run classes in family planning and birthing," and "when we go to church camp, we get advice, doctors talking to a big group."

5. Decision-making about birthing place

Women were asked about their personal choices and others involved in decision-making on delivery choices, the knowledge that affected decisions and the effects of these decisions on them. One participant described a delay in seeking care for a family member living in Goroka:

"In Goroka where we're staying, that's, what will I call, [CHW's daughter-in-law]... she was trying to give birth to fourth-born, and all day she didn't tell the husband that she was feeling labour pains, so that we can bring her to the hospital, so in the night, the husband came over to both of us saying, "My wife is feeling pains, she was to give birth to her baby." So Josca tell him, "Go and

tell the owner of the car to rush her to the hospital.” But the thing is, she was bleeding already. And then we rushed her up, because we were living... you know, you’ll have to go up a little bit of a mountain to go to the car. And then when we were walking up, I mean we go to the house, I could see that something dropping there. So we were trying our best to help her up and then put her on the car. But maybe she was feeling that the baby will come, so she said we will leave it and go back to the house. So we were still talking up there too, so the husband would get the ambulance to come and get her, but... One of Josca’s sisters, she came down. She just gave birth to the baby on the way, the road.”

Another described the influence of health worker advice on when to travel to Goroka: “When I went to the clinic, Denmark told me that this is my last month, and next month you will be dropping your baby, so you must go.”

A husband discussed the decision to leave early for his wife to give birth at Okapa: “I was thinking of the second one, so took her early, so she was there for 2 weeks before the baby arrived. Plenty of time.” He had worried when his wife gave birth on the way to Ivingoi the previous time: “...very concerned, far away. What if either have a problem? Very worried. When wife delivers, I can’t go close. But I stayed near so could hear what was happening. Stressed. When she was sorted out and told me it’s a girl and okay, I was relieved.”

And regarding seeking Goroka Base Hospital (GBH) care for their first baby: “My mother, father, uncles and aunts told that when wife deliver, if not proper then wife swell and die, or baby broken arms or legs, so better in hospital,” and: “It was our first baby, so I worry she might lose the baby, or a village midwife might not deliver it properly and there might be problems, so we went to GBH.”

A father described the decision to send his unmarried daughter to Goroka Hospital for her first birth: “Health Department advice is for first born to send to GBH. This is the same advice for any woman. I sent her mother with her to assist... They borrowed a small house – one room and bed – for two weeks.” Then for her second unmarried pregnancy: “I discussed with her mother, it was the second birth. It’s expensive to go to town, and we have food here and have experience, so we decided she’d stay.” The father also said, when asked about his daughter’s thoughts on the place of delivery: “She is the child, so she agreed with her parents. When the baby has grown up, [she] can continue at school. And when she finished school, she can look after me.”

6. a. Attitudes to travelling to Goroka and using hospital services (advantages and barriers – if hospital birth)

Women who used maternity facilities were asked about their experiences using these, what services were offered and whether they would choose to use them again. Our interpreter thought traditions and fear of the unknown were a barrier to community women seeking facility births: “Yeah, we can tell them to come to town to give birth, but their thinking is just the same as their old, old, you know, grandmother, the one who have passed by, they’ve passed through this system ‘til now.”

One woman described the costs of a Goroka birth: “The hospital, we had to pay for the bed, and where we stayed, we had to help the owner of the house to buy food and wood.” She and her husband planned subsequent, lower risk births at Okapa and Ivingoi, which cost her less in travel, accommodation and clinic fees.

Another described the reassurance of expert help: “Baby number 3 was born in 2005. I went to Goroka Hospital because I had family to stay with... My legs swelled up late in pregnancy, and this was the first time this had happened to me... the doctor said it was normal, that I’m a bit older now.”

b. Attitudes to using Paiga Clinic services and/or home birth (advantages and barriers – if home birth).

Women birthing at home were asked about the decision and experience and whether they would choose to do so again. One reported what others had said about the advantages of the hospital that she hadn't experienced: "Other ladies say hospital is nice and clean; the *smallhaus* is dirty. The hospital is relaxed, help you and clean everything."

Another woman compared the two experiences and said she thought that for normal births, it was the same, both hospital staff and the women assisting with births at home were helpful.

A husband described the decision to birth at home for their fourth child: "For the fourth baby, we had idea and experience, we were thinking at home, so I made a *smallhaus*. Three children already, so we were experienced. We discussed and we decided together. Expensive to go to town, and she had experience in birth," and "...thinking of three kids too, no one to feed and look after, siblings have their own. My concern was for them too."

7. Use of a Goroka-based maternity waiting home

Women were asked about their future personal use of a MWH in Goroka if such a facility were made available, and what would assist them to access the facility.

Regarding participants' future use of a MWH: "Very happy with this idea, thank you. This is very good for women from the village." "I would be happy to use it, and when the time came, I would go straight there." Participants also reported they would use the MWH in preference to staying with family living in Goroka because it was easier. "Relatives are difficult for kids and school this year. Not difficult to come and stay [at MWH] if we have water and table for food. This makes easier and very [helpful]."

Regarding MWH facilities: "If it's a house with utensils, then easy."

Regarding travel to the MWH: Some women expressed the desire to bring a family member with them to the MWH, others reported they would be alright to travel alone.

Regarding other women in the community using the MWH: "It will help them, make it easier to stay close to the hospital," and "inform the women in the village, expectant mums, if they know they will be happy and want to use it. For some women it is hard to stay with family in town, not always welcome."

"I think if we have got these modern facilities in Paiga, it will help them, I don't know. Or they will still give birth in their *smallhaus*... you know, they like to build their *smallhaus* and give birth inside... But likewise, if you go in, and if we can talk to them and give some teaching to them, maybe it will help them."

"If informed, then I think yes. As young ladies now are advised to go to town, so they would be happy to come to a maternity waiting home."

"I think they all want to give birth at hospital."

"If you make the maternity waiting home, we can freely go, stay and get to hospital."

Regarding other women with a different *tok ples* using the MWH, participants felt accepting of women from South Gimi also using the facility, but one reported discomfort sharing the facility with women from elsewhere: "I wouldn't be happy with that – they speak differently."

From a husband, regarding using the MWH: “It’s the very last [baby] – five years long and hard work in the meantime. It will be good for her to have nursing. I want her to come early and rest and wait. Important to rest for her and baby, and hospital for last baby.”

From the CHW: “I am experienced in sending people to Goroka and very happy to have [the MWH]. The issue of lack of family to accommodate, so it’s very expensive, about K50 for a small room. If block of land, can have vegetable garden so have food, therefore help in other small ways, leave with medicines for home. It’s a very good idea and I appreciate.”

When asked how to coordinate use of the MWH from the village: “First, I would send a referral letter from the village to send to the clinic. They come to Goroka but they don’t get medicines or visit GBH because they can’t afford treatment. They die, or don’t come see me after.”

Regarding antenatal care at Paigatasa Clinic: “...it’s a very remote area. Water is very important, and AT Projects excellent to have provided. So they take medicines when they are with me, they don’t throw away, I am very very happy. I can’t tell what’s in my heart to have water at the clinic.”

Regarding transport to Goroka: “I suggest... PMV costs K12 per person and they [PMV] take two to three people, so they don’t go. Could we get a vehicle kept for Paiga transport, suitable for the community?”

8. Focus group feedback on practical implementation of a MWH project

General attitude towards use of a MWH: “...the problem is that we don’t have a road. So the APOs [aid post officers or CHWs] have given referrals to go to Okapa, to town, but some have passed away on the road, so we really appreciate this idea of setting something up in the town area... when we have that, all the expenses and everything we are facing in the town area will be a little bit ok for us.”

Informing the community about the MWH facility and who it is for: (male respondent) “We got certain places where we do market, and sometimes we do awareness in the community. That’s where we can let people know, it’s not for everyone to come and stay, but for sick persons.” (female respondent): “We have some friends from Gimi and other areas... We can pass message around to friends we have met when we get together in the market and that kind of thing.”

On problems that might be encountered in the use of the MWH: “We will not entertain the people who will come for the personal issues, who will come to get some personal things and want to stay. There will be a guard in the area who will be responsible for identifying the referral letters of those who come. So we use only that for people who come to use the waiting house.”

On unmarried mothers accessing services: “As you heard, there is a problem with the young women who don’t have a husband. It will be very helpful for them to stay in the MWH. So you know they [the community] ignore the people who don’t have a husband and just get pregnant on the way and that. They ignore people like that, so it’s very easy for [unmarried mothers] to go [to the MWH], so that’s a good idea.”

On encouraging women who don’t currently use health services to access the MWH: “...we could go and just message in the church, and the market area, so we can advise the ladies who really don’t understand, to use the clinic for family planning or some other treatment, for their health. If we advise them on that, and if they get our advice and get the referral letter, then they will come ... so we’ll just announce the waiting house like this... ‘you can come and check up’, like this, at the church gathering and some other places where all the ladies will gather.”

On whose name the MWH and land should be kept in: “We can go to the Lands Department and get the title. After buying the land, we get the owner of the land, and do the agreement form and all sign.”

“If there is any problem, we put in clinic name or something, it will be very high, people will be thinking this is government departments wanting to buy. We can just mention one name [Josca] and everything is done in that name, and we can provide all the services we mentioned, and we can attend to the people who have the identity can come and stay. If we go public there will be a lot of problem again. So this is the idea, the good idea.”

“If some problem came to Josca, then the kids can look after, and some of Josca’s family can come and stand at the back of the kids.” “Josca [also] has an extended family, like Job’s family and Josca’s 3 brothers.” And: “They are thinking that we can’t sell the land because it’s not our private, it’s something to the community and it’s under Josca’s name, so if something happened to Josca, the family would come in and look after it.”

On setting up the MWH: “For the building, I think we can get these people [AT Projects] to do it, and they can do everything within 12 months, so I suggest we ask them to do the building. They have good ideas and good design, and they can do everything for us. For the caretaker, and the persons who come there, if we have one of the house like AT does, for the sick persons, and another for the caretaker, and we do another 2 or 3 bedroom house for you [PAIGA committee] to come in and out of the area, so you can have access to come instead of buying hotel and everything.”

On transport to the MWH: “...now the bus fare from Ke’efu to Goroka is K12, so Denmark, he normally does with the sick people, when they have serious illness... they normally use the ambulance for Henagaru or Goroka.” “[The ambulance] will help the pregnant women too.”

On women using the MWH engaging in craft-making and learning other skills while they wait for the birth: “That’s a good idea... when they are here, they can make bilum and you can sell it for them down in Australia, and you can send them money back, or they can sell it here in Goroka... they will do nothing [while at the MWH], so they can do this while waiting for the time. And when the money comes it will help them have some money for foods and for the transport.” And: “Mercyworks is the best for this kind of training.” Health education and literacy and numeracy training was also discussed as optional activities while women wait for babies’ births at the MWH.

Ranking exercise re: MWH services

The focus group was then asked to rank 15 aspects or services that could be provided in a MWH in order of perceived importance, with 1. being most important. The following list was negotiated and agreed upon by the group after an explanation of each item was provided:

1. Health worker on site (NB: the group said that a CHW, nursing or midwifery *student* would be acceptable)
2. Secure housing
3. Walking distance to hospital
4. Money for transport
5. Transport to hospital
6. Accommodation for other sick people
7. Accommodation for family
8. *Bilum*-making and other money-making projects for waiting women
9. Mother and baby gifts

10. Money for hospital fees
11. Food
12. Health education (maternal and child health and family planning)
13. Childcare on site
14. Record-keeping
15. *Tok ples* (Fore- and Gimi-speaking)-only guests.

Limitations of the study

Selection of scoping study participants was made by the Paigatasa Clinic Committee, and were all *wantoks* of the Committee, and depended also on women's availability for travel to Goroka. Therefore, participants did not include any South Gimi women, and may not be fully representative of community views and experiences. Other limitations include the number of participants able to be accommodated at the guesthouse, and time restrictions limiting individual and group feedback and discussion. Interpreters were experienced, due to being used extensively for other studies and less formal communications in the community, but had not been formally trained as interpreters, so it is possible that there were misunderstandings during interpretation. It is also possible that the young woman who travelled with her father thought that her interview may not be kept confidential from him, despite the information given in the privacy statement.

In the focus group, men tended to talk first, and women needed to be invited to give their opinions. The young women were shy and tended to stay silent even when asked to talk. Traditional social structures were likely at play in the group, inhibiting some voices from speaking freely.

Discussion Points

1. Women participants were experienced in utilising various means of delivering their babies, including home births and assisted facility births, and some had experienced complications of pregnancy and/or labour. They were therefore knowledgeable and informative participants to this scoping study and their views and inputs could be considered representative of the broader community.
2. Women participants, their male relatives and the local CHW made it clear in interviews that the barriers to facility births identified in the 2010 survey still exist (i.e. distance, transport, cost, place to stay), and added information on family advice for or against seeking a hospital birth as an important influence on decision-making.
3. Participants also informed that Goroka Hospital is currently the facility of choice for women who decide not to give birth at home, especially for first-time mothers and those seeking family completion.
4. Local CHWs appear not to be making referrals to Okapa and the other maternity centres in the district currently, maybe because of lack of EMONC services in these places, or perhaps because of deterioration of the district's rural facilities.
5. Many community women do not seek antenatal care at Paigatasa Clinic and therefore may not get professional advice on where to give birth for optimal health and safety.
6. Women who had had negative experiences or complications with deliveries often used hospital for subsequent births.
7. Women and their families are using modern sexual and reproductive health services, practices and beliefs and mixing them with traditional birthing practices and beliefs as it best suits their situations.

8. Traditional sexual and reproductive health education, as reported by participants, does not appear to include how to space children or prevent a pregnancy. Formal school education appears to lack sexual and reproductive health information and young people may finish school without any education on this topic. Health workers, church camp and family members represent the three most important sources of modern sexual and reproductive health information.
9. Young unmarried pregnant women were identified as a stigmatised, vulnerable and disadvantaged group due to being without husbands to help with costs and support choices around birth, and whose families could be disapproving and punitive in their approaches to the pregnancy and birth.
10. Young women reported little opportunity to learn about modern sexual and reproductive health prior to their first pregnancy, apart from some information being passed down from older siblings and relatives, and this issue is flagged as a major concern for the current generation of adolescent girls and young women at increased risk of pregnancy while staying away from their families to finish school. This is reflected in the older participants' and interviewers' attitudes to unwed young mothers. It is possible that the two youngest women participants felt shame and embarrassment talking about family planning knowledge and use, especially outside marriage, because of strong cultural taboos, and this may have impacted on the study team's ability to gain insight into actual knowledge and sources of information and decision-making on FP uptake.
11. All interviewees were overwhelmingly positive about the concept of a MWH and supported the project going ahead. The women who were likely to have more children all reported that they would use the facility in the future.
12. Most important aspects of a MWH for the group were: health worker onsite, secure housing, and transport to the MWH and to hospital. Individuals also reported that the facility should include a reliable water source, a garden and facilities to cook, and accommodation for other family travelling with pregnant community women. Women participants liked the idea of bilum-making and other activities useful for income generation to be made available at the MWH.
13. Record-keeping was not explained to the focus group during the ranking exercise other than to say there would be records of use and expenses kept, and was not considered to be high priority by the group. However, this element of MWH maintenance is considered of importance to the investigators in order to gather data on its use, monitor expenses, evaluate and report the success of the MWH project to supporters in meeting its goals.
14. The group had already developed some ideas regarding practical operation of the MWH and were able to contribute further planning advice, including an idea about potentially using the Okapa ambulance for transport.
15. The group thought that ownership of the MWH land should be in Josca Ariva's name in his role as Community Liaison. The PAIGA committee later thought this plan carried too many risks. Unfortunately, this point of contention has been made irrelevant by Josca's recent and untimely death, but the community have indicated their support for his family to act as caretakers for the facility, and this is supported by the PAIGA committee.

Conclusions and Recommendations

1. The MWH Project has the full and active support of community members interviewed, and participants are likely to be representative of many of the attitudes and behaviours of the community represented.
2. Efforts should be made during outreach activities to contact more remotely living and less educated women, including those with less family support and unmarried mothers.
3. Modern family planning knowledge is integral to women's and their families' sexual and reproductive health, and this area must be integrated into educational activities in the community and MWH, and also targeted towards unmarried young women and men.
4. Stakeholders to involve in further development of the MWH project include:
 - a. Community CHWs (keep informed, keep educating including update on Department of Health/Provincial Health Authority sexual and reproductive health policies and guidelines, support their work, support next generation of CHWs).
 - b. Goroka Hospital, Okapa HWs in other rural health centres and relevant PHA staff for optimal linked care, collaboration and ongoing updated information about services.
 - c. Community health volunteers – to be identified in each village, enlisted, trained and supported as an essential component of MWH outreach activities, and to provide ongoing monitoring data re: women appropriately identified and referred to the facility.
 - d. Community leaders including ward representatives, church leaders and Paigatasa Clinic Committee, and MP for Okapa if possible.
 - e. Other maternal and child health care providers in Goroka and wider PNG, including NGOs such as CARE, Mercyworks and Send Hope Not Flowers, to identify common goals and possible links with other established programs and resources.
 - f. Users of the MWH and their families, for feedback to improve the facility and outreach project.
 - g. Pauline Ariva and her family as caretakers of the facility, to support their ongoing upkeep, monitoring and evaluation of use.
 - h. PAIGA Community Association, which is yet to be established, but which will provide overarching guidance on community projects including the MWH, and which will be the collective landowners of the MWH.
 - i. PAIGA Committee, for ongoing fundraising, support, administration, monitoring, evaluation and reporting on the MWH project.
 - j. Goroka-based health worker or health student to identify as live-in health officer for the facility in exchange for board.
 - k. Fundraising supporter base in Australia to update with project progress and keep involved.
5. Phone use among young people was highlighted as a sexual and reproductive health safety issue by older study participants with adolescent children. It is worth exploring mobile technology, gaining momentum in PNG, as a project opportunity instead of a threat. Technology to support the MWH project may include a mobile network of village health volunteers to notify MWH caretaker of referrals, mobile-based sexual and reproductive health education for community youth, in-house MWH database for monitoring and evaluation, and web-based publication of summarised data and other updates on the MWH project for our stakeholders, including the Paiga Clinic catchment community and Australian supporters.
6. Buying a suitable car as transport for the community MWH is currently out of PAIGA's budget, and the community lost its professional driver when Josca Ariva passed away. However, there may be partnership opportunities with Goroka Hospital/PHA vehicles, Okapa

HC and its ambulance, CARE or Susmamas outreach projects, or even PMV drivers local to the MWH land location.

7. PNGIMR and its Australian partners may have researchers interested in working with PAIGA on a formal assessment of MWH use and outcomes. Dr Angela Kelly-Hanku and Dr Janet Gare, SRH research colleagues from PNGINR, are aware of this project and offered some useful input at its inception.

Acknowledgements

Tanya Gerrie (PAIGA Treasurer) is co-investigator and co-author of this scoping study.

PAIGA Committee supported the scoping study and made helpful comments on the draft paper.

The late Josca Ariva and his wife Pauline Ariva were interpreters for this study. Pauline, *sori tru* for your and your family's loss, Josca is sorely missed by us all, and there is a proposal to name the MWH after him.

Paigatasa and South Gimi communities, health workers, and Paigatasa Clinic Committee supported this study and we are grateful.

AT Projects (Steve and Miriam Layton and their staff) housed and fed us during the study, and offered many helpful insights into the Goroka context. We look forward to an ongoing partnership.

Dr Waima Wiai and Dr Freda Wemin of Goroka Hospital and Dr Max Manape of EHPHA / Department of Public Health indicated their support of the MWH project, and Mr Kollen Koti of MS International Goroka Office gave much useful information and resources. Dr Janet Gare (ADir) and Dr Angela Kelly-Hantu (Dir) of the PNGIMR SHR Unit offered their time and suggestions. Thank you to Miriam Layton's community who invited us to their wonderful mumu and gave us some suggestions for locating MWH land, and the inspiring ladies who let Tanya and me gate-crash part of their 2018 Annual PNG Women in Leadership meeting at AT Projects guesthouse.

Dr Bronwen Morrison,
PAIGA Chair, 26 June 2021

Appendix A: Study Protocol

1.1. **Name:** Paigatasa Maternity Waiting Home Scoping Study

1.2. **Investigators:** Bronwen Morrison and Tanya Gerrie

2. Contextualizing the need for the study

2.1. **Context:** Previous study showed high maternal and infant perinatal death rate in Paigatasa and South Gimi communities. Currently, neither facilities nor skilled birth attendants are available for CEmONC in Okapa District, therefore a safe Goroka-based waiting home for women to stay before delivering in Goroka Hospital is proposed.

2.2. **Literature review:** Limited PNG-specific research on waiting homes, but 2 new successful models exist. Successful also in settings including Africa, South America and SE Asia. Lessons include ensuring antenatal care, informing women of service, and overcoming barriers such as transport and partner/family consent factors. Blood taboos may be a factor in women not accessing transport late in pregnancy. Young people's access to SRH information and services in PNG.

2.3. **Research question and study objectives:** What are women's and their families' thoughts on use of a waiting home, for and against, and what could make this project a success or failure?

3. Qualitative study design

3.1. **Study approach:** Semi-structured interviews and focus groups with community women and clinic committee.

3.2. **Study team:** Bronwen Morrison and Tanya Gerrie

3.2.1. **Collaborators: Women Participants:** W1, W2, W3, W4. **Clinic Committee participants:** C1 (interviewer 1), C2 (Interviewer 2), C3, C4.

3.2.2. **Advisory board:** PAIGA Committee and Paiga clinic committee.

3.3. Study location and participants

3.3.1. **Study location justification:** Goroka rather than Paiga community due to investigators' time constraints. Community participants to be hosted at guesthouse with investigators.

3.3.2. **Accessing the locale:** Travel support for participants (PMV), air travel for investigators.

3.3.3. **Participant selection and recruitment:** Josca Ariva, community liaison, to use participant recruitment guide to recruit and arrange timing of Goroka visit.

3.4. **Data collection:** Recording of interviews and note-taking.

3.4.1. **Methods:** Mixed implementation and phenomenological research for local context analysis through semi-structured interviews and focus group discussion.

3.4.2. **Procedure:** See Topic Guide for interviews and focus group.

3.5. Socio-ethical considerations

3.5.1. **Cultural and linguistic considerations:** A Tok Pisin/Fore/Gimi interpreter will be required depending on which women accept the invitation to participate.

3.5.2. **Informed consent:** Women will be formally consented with a read-aloud and interpreted statement on the purpose of the study, likely benefits and risks of participation, and confidentiality.

3.5.3. Risks and benefits: Risks are involved in travelling away from community for the study and possible jealousy responses from other community members not chosen for study. Benefits include a small gift, opportunity to discuss issues of safe motherhood in a comfortable environment, and the study will lead to a new community resource and more safer hospital births if findings support the maternity waiting home project.

3.5.4. Confidentiality and data storage: Data will be kept in Australia on investigators' electronic devices. Participants will be de-identified in any published or distributed materials stemming from this study.

3.5.5. Compensation: Participants' travel, meal and accommodation expenses will be met, and small gifts given for participation (solar lights and other small items).

3.6. Data analysis

3.6.1. Data preparation: Interviews and focus groups will be transcribed in English by investigators.

3.6.2. Analysis procedure: Key issues, representative stories and common themes, including cultural context and contemporary local challenges to health care access, will be identified and discussed. Community preferences and potential solutions to issues raised will be described and used to inform future MWH planning.

3.7. Cost and timescale

3.7.1. Timescale: July 2018 - Prepare and conduct study; August 2018 – Write report and application for funding grant.

3.7.2. Budget: \$6,880K.

3.8. Conflicts of interest: Investigators – none identified; community liaison will personally benefit from project implementation because identified by community as best caretaker for MWH.

3.9. Appendices

3.9.1. Research tools (e.g. topic guides, observation guide, survey)

3.9.2. Information sheets

3.9.3. Informed consent forms

3.9.4. Permission and collaboration letters

Appendix B: Topic Guide (women's individual interviews)

9. Personal decision-making re: birthing choices
 - Elicit story of birth/s, self or sisters/-in-law.
10. Knowledge and attitudes to sexual and reproductive health (self and family)
 - What did you know about family planning, pregnancy and giving birth before you first became pregnant?
 - What did your family/friends/other people tell you?
 - What did you learn about FP, pregnancy and giving birth during your pregnancy/ies?
11. Traditional attitudes to safe motherhood
 - What are the community's traditional attitudes to FP, pregnancy and giving birth?
 - Tell us about any traditions/taboo that affected your pregnancy and childbirth.

- Tell us about... [women's blood and birth fluids, birth position, treatment of mother and baby after birth, female initiation, communication between family members, support and influence of husband.]
- 12. Church attitude to safe motherhood (opportunities and threats)
 - What does your church teach about FP, pregnancy and giving birth?
- 13. Decision-making about birthing place
 - Did you feel you had a choice about where to give birth?
 - What made you decide to give birth at [place]?
 - Who else was involved in making this decision?
 - What personal knowledge helped you make the decision?
 - What were the advantages and disadvantages of this birthing place for you?
- 14. *Attitudes to travelling to Goroka and using hospital services (advantages and barriers)
 - What were the good and bad things about travelling to Goroka Hospital for delivery?
 - What services were provided around your delivery in the hospital?
 - What do you think about Goroka Hospital delivery services?
- 15. OR *Attitudes to using Paiga Clinic services and/or home birth (advantages and barriers).
 - What were the good and bad things about giving birth in Paiga?
 - What services were provided around your delivery in Paiga?
 - What do you think about those services?
- 16. Use of a Goroka-based maternity waiting home
 - If a maternity waiting home were available during your next pregnancy, would you use it?
 - Why/why not?
 - What would help you access a maternity waiting home service in Goroka?

Appendix C: Topic Guide (men's individual interviews)

- 17. Personal decision-making re: birthing choices
 - Elicit story of wife's (+/- daughter's) birth/s.
- 18. Knowledge and attitudes to sexual and reproductive health (self and family)
 - What did you know about family planning, pregnancy and giving birth before your wife/daughter first became pregnant?
 - What did your family/friends/other people tell you?
 - What did you learn about FP, pregnancy and giving birth during your wife/daughter's pregnancy/ies?
- 19. Traditional attitudes to safe motherhood
 - What are the community's traditional attitudes to FP, pregnancy and giving birth?
 - Tell us about any traditions/taboo that affected your wife/ pregnancy and childbirth.
 - Tell us about... [women's blood and birth fluids, birth position, treatment of mother and baby after birth, female initiation, communication between family members, support and influence with wife.]
- 20. Church attitude to safe motherhood (opportunities and threats)
 - What does your church teach about FP, pregnancy and giving birth?
- 21. Decision-making about birthing place
 - Did you and your wife have a choice about where she could give birth?
 - What made you decide to support your wife giving birth at [place]?
 - Who else was involved in making this decision?
 - What personal knowledge helped you make the decision?
 - What were the advantages and disadvantages of this birthing place for your wife?
- 22. *Attitudes to travelling to Goroka and using hospital services (advantages and barriers)
 - What were the good and bad things about travelling to Goroka Hospital for delivery?

- What services were provided around your wife/daughter's delivery in the hospital?
- What do you think about Goroka Hospital delivery services?
- 23. OR *Attitudes to using Paiga Clinic services and/or home birth (advantages and barriers).
 - What were the good and bad things about your wife/daughter giving birth in Paiga?
 - What services were provided around your wife/daughter's delivery in Paiga?
 - What do you think about those services?
- 24. Use of a Goroka-based maternity waiting home
 - If a maternity waiting home were available during your wife/daughter's next pregnancy, would you encourage her to use it?
 - Why/why not?
 - What would help your wife/daughter access a maternity waiting home service in Goroka?

Appendix D: Topic Guide (focus group)

- 25. Ideas for ensuring use of maternity waiting home
 - What are the advantages of a Goroka maternity waiting home for all pregnant women in Paiga and Gimi?
 - What are the barriers to Paiga and Gimi women using such a service?
 - What support and services would increase women's use of a waiting home?
 - What revenue-raising activities could pregnant women engage in while staying at a waiting home?
 - What would need to be done in the community to ensure all women have knowledge of the service and know when to access it?
- 26. Ranking exercise – important aspects to include in MWH:
 - Garden food
 - Secure housing
 - Billum-making and other income projects
 - Money for transport
 - Only *tok ples* guests
 - Health worker on site
 - Walking distance to hospital
 - Accommodation for family escorts
 - Childcare on site
 - Record-keeping
 - Assistance with hospital fees
 - Education on mother and baby health and family planning
 - Mother and baby gifts (e.g. baby wrap, nappy, soap, bucket, etc)
 - Accommodation for other sick community members
 - Transport to hospital
 - Other: _____
- 27. Engagement with and opinion of PAIGA activities to date
 - School support
 - Clinic support
 - Home toilet installations
 - Scholarships
 - Gimi projects
 - Other

Appendix E: Consent to Participate in Study

Bronwen Morrison and Tanya Gerrie are conducting this study on behalf of PAIGA organisation and Paiga and Gimi communities.

The purpose is to explore your thoughts and ideas on use of a maternity waiting home, and what could make this project a success or a failure.

Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw from the study at any time or decide not to answer specific questions without problems.

We will ask each of you some questions for 1-2 hours, and the group together for another 1-2 hours, over the next 2 days. We might have further questions for each of you after the first interviews. We will use a voice recorder and notepad to record your answers.

All information you give us will be kept in a secure location in Australia. Your name will be removed from any published information so no-one can identify you from it.

The only known risk in participation is your travel to and from Goroka for the interviews. Benefits of participation include probable further community resource development, and some small gifts that we would like to give you to acknowledge your support, time and effort in travelling to Goroka.

The study has been explained to me / I have read the information sheet and I agree to take part.

Tok Pisin words used in this report

Bilum: String bag and traditional handicraft of the PNG Highlands, customarily given by a woman to the man she will marry. *Hausman*: A gathering of community men to impart wisdom and learning to younger men and boys, sometimes during initiation or before marriage. *Hausmeri*: A gathering of community women to impart wisdom and learning to younger women and girls, sometimes during initiation or before marriage. *Smallhaus*: A very small hut made of natural materials, sited away from the family house, for a woman to give birth in if she is birthing at home. *Tok ples*: Local language.

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- ^x It is noted that the word 'doctor' in translation from South Fore or Tok Pisin can mean any trained health worker and is commonly used to describe a doctor, nurse, midwife or CHW.